

CQD-Based Electrochemical Immunosensor for Sensitive D-Dimer Detection in Thrombosis and COVID-19

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ABSTRACT

Thrombosis, a leading cause of heart attacks, strokes, and venous thromboembolism (VTE), contributes to 25% of global deaths. Factors like aging and immobility increase VTE risk. D-dimer (DD), whose elevated levels indicate conditions such as pulmonary embolism and severe COVID-19, is a key biomarker for thrombus detection, predicting higher mortality risks. Traditional DD detection methods are time-consuming and costly. Emerging point-of-care (POCT) biosensors offer faster, cost-effective alternatives, utilizing electrochemical or optical detection and nanostructured films. This study aims to develop a sensitive, label-free electrochemical immunosensor for DD detection using carbon quantum dots (CQDs) functionalized electrodes and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). CQDs enhance electrode sensitivity by improving conductivity and providing anchoring sites for monoclonal antibody (Ab). The biosensor was made by activating a carbon screen printed electrode with KOH, adding amino groups via 3-Aminopropyltriethoxysilane, linking CQDs with 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carbodiimide/*N*-hydroxysuccinimide (EDC/NHS), and immobilizing DD Ab on CQD surface. Raman spectroscopy and EIS confirmed successful functionalization and increased resistance with Ab and bovine serum albumin layers. The biosensor effectively detected DD antigens, with a calibration curve ranging from 10 to 1000 ng mL⁻¹ and a low limit of detection of 13.4 ng mL⁻¹. CQDs improved sensitivity, and low Ab concentrations reduced costs. This CQD-based impedance immunosensor offers a practical approach for early thrombosis detection and monitoring diseases like VTE and COVID-19 at the point of care.

KEYWORDS: carbon quantum dot, d-dimer, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, immunosensor, cardiovascular diseases

1. Introduction

Thrombosis is a leading cause of death globally, responsible for 1 in 4 deaths [1]. It is the primary underlying cause of most heart attacks, strokes, and venous thromboembolism (VTE), which includes deep vein thrombosis (DVT) and pulmonary embolism (PE) [2]. VTE, characterized by inappropriate blood clot forming thrombus, leads to significant morbidity and mortality across all ethnic groups, genders, and ages. In the USA, it is the third most common life-threatening cardiovascular disease [3]. As risk factors such as advanced age, immobility, surgery, and obesity become more prevalent, VTE is increasingly becoming a major public health concern. Fibrin is the primary component of a thrombus. When fibrin dissolves, it forms specific degradation products, including D-dimer (DD) among others, which can be measured in blood and plasma. This measurement uses monoclonal antibodies (Ab) targeting epitopes on the DD fragment [4]. Since DD is not artificially generated during blood collection, its presence accurately reflects in vivo hemostatic activity, and its absence effectively excludes the presence of an intravascular thrombus. Values greater than 500 ng mL^{-1} of DD suggest the possibility of PE. However, DD levels tend to increase with age, leading to a higher incidence of false positives in patients over 50 years old, which reduces the test's specificity in this demographic [5]. To mitigate false positives, an age-adjusted threshold is applied, calculated as the patient's age (if over 50 years) multiplied by 10 ng mL^{-1} . This adjustment effectively increases the detection range up to $1 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ [6].

Recently, with the emergence of COVID-19, this biomarker has gained significant interest within the scientific community. Its usefulness has been demonstrated in indicating the severity of the infection and in monitoring the disease's progression [7]. Clinical studies revealed that patients with severe COVID-19 had significantly higher levels of DD compared to those with milder cases. DD levels above $2 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ upon hospital admission could indicate a mortality risk of 92.3%,

regardless of the patient's symptom severity [8]. Consequently, DD content in the blood can be utilized as a prognostic marker for hospital mortality in COVID-19 patients.

Quantitative assays for determining DD levels in clinical laboratories are well established. Among these, the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) is notable for its high sensitivity and is considered the gold standard for DD testing [9]. Automated immunoassay methods, such as latex agglutination, are also widely used [10]. However, these traditional methods have significant drawbacks, including long reaction times and high costs [11]. In response to the growing demand for point-of-care (POCT) DD testing, new detection methods have emerged in recent years. These innovative biosensors offer faster and more user-friendly solutions for emergency situations [12]. Additionally, they are more cost-effective and utilize electrochemical or optical detection principles, often incorporating nanostructured films [13].

The fabrication of biosensors with layer-by-layer controlled molecular architecture has been explored extensively. The primary goal is to immobilize biomolecules that can exclusively recognize the target analyte, ensuring high sensitivity and selectivity [14]. Among these biosensors, immunosensors are particularly noteworthy, relying on the specific identification of target antigens through their corresponding Ab [15-17]. Detection methods for these biosensors can be optical, electrical, or electrochemical, depending on the type of nanostructure used. Electrochemical detection techniques, in particular, offer ease of use and can significantly reduce test duration. This is achieved by measuring the current between the functionalized working electrode (immunosensor) and a reference electrode. Electrochemical detection-based immunosensors have been investigated in numerous analyses due to their specificity, simplicity, portability, and general disposability, making them suitable for in situ or automated detection [18].

Despite their significant advantages, few electrochemical methods utilizing detection techniques such as cyclic voltammetry (CV) [19], amperometry [20], potentiometry [21, 22], impedimetric [23], AC electrokinetics (ACEK)-enhanced capacitive sensing [24], differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) [25-27], square wave voltammetry (SWV) [28], and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) [29-32] have been reported in recent years for DD detection. These methods rely on signal decay caused by the impediment to ionic or redox reporter flow from the solution to the working electrode interface and ion diffusion within the film. The extent of this impediment is influenced by the level of DD associated with the Ab on the working electrode [30]. Among these methods, EIS is a popular alternative technique for sensor design, offering several advantages. It reduces surface fouling, is unaffected by ambient light interference (unlike optical sensors), and provides stable, reliable sensor readings at lower voltage levels [33, 34]. Furthermore, EIS provides a deeper understanding of sensor performance by extracting key electrical parameters through a simplified electrical model that represents the sensor's behavior using basic circuit elements [35]. This approach enhances analysis and facilitates optimization of the sensor's design and functionality.

Recently, the use of metallic and inorganic nanoparticles has gained momentum due to their ability to enhance the electrochemical properties of immunosensors while also benefiting from their biocompatibility [36]. However, many of these nanoparticles exhibit significant hydrophobicity, which results in poor solubility in aqueous solutions and promotes aggregate formation. As a consequence, their uniform decoration with other metal nanoparticles or further functionalization is hindered. In contrast, carbon quantum dots (CQDs) have garnered significant attention from the scientific community for their potential in electrode functionalization to enhance electrical signals in chemical and biological sensors [37, 38]. The surface of CQD nanostructures

contains numerous polar groups, such as carboxylic residues, whose presence varies depending on the synthetic method employed. These groups offer excellent water solubility and act as anchoring sites for additional functionalization with other desired species or improve affinity for specific substances during detection processes [39]. In electrochemical applications, CQDs offer crucial characteristics such as electronic conductivity, physical sites for electron transfer, high surface density, and photoactive reaction centers, significantly boosting the performance of electrochemical sensors [40].

The aim of this study is to develop a highly sensitive, label-free electrochemical immunosensor for detecting DD biomarker. This will be achieved using CQD-functionalized electrodes with covalently attached DD Ab, and employing EIS as the detection technique. By integrating CQDs onto a screen-printed electrode (SPE) surface, we achieve a higher density of nanoparticles, significantly enhancing the interaction surface. This results in increased Ab loading and improved conductivity of the electrochemical immunosensor. Consequently, this research presents an innovative and practical approach for the early detection of thrombosis-related diseases. It introduces a highly sensitive method for detecting the DD biomarker in serum samples, facilitating rapid screening and monitoring of diseases such as VTE and COVID-19 at the point of care.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials and Chemicals

Citric acid (CA, 99%), urea, phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), diethyl ether (98%), *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF, 99.9%), ether, ethyl acetate, 1-ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carbodiimide (EDC, 98%), *N*-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS, 98%), 3-Aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES, 98%), 2-(*N*-morpholino) ethanesulfonic acid (MES, 99%), potassium hydroxide

(KOH), bovine serum albumin (BSA), and absolute ethanol. The reagents were all obtained from Sigma Aldrich, Germany. Milli-Q water grade ($0.055 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$) was used in all the synthesis processes. The DD monoclonal antibody DD189cc (5.6 mg mL^{-1}) and DD antigen 8D70 (5.8 mg mL^{-1}) were obtained from Hytest. Unless otherwise stated, all chemicals were used as received, without further modifications.

Fig. 1. A schematic diagram of the sensor fabrication process, detailing each step from the treatment of the screen-printed electrode to the final Ab-coated electrode.

2.2 Carbon Quantum Dots (CQDs) Synthesis

CQDs were synthesized via hydrothermal synthesis following the methodology outlined by Paulo-Mirasol et al. [41] Initially, 1.051 g of CA was dissolved in 10 mL of DMF, followed by the addition of 2 g of urea. The mixture was stirred until a clear, homogeneous solution was achieved. This solution was then transferred to a 50 mL Teflon-lined autoclave reactor and heated at $160 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 16 h. After hydrothermal synthesis, the CQDs were precipitated using a mixture of ether and ethyl acetate in a 4:1 v/v ratio and subsequently centrifuged at 4500 rpm. The resulting precipitate was dried and stored in an air tight container at $4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

2.3 Sensor Fabrication

The sensor was fabricated through a series of carefully controlled steps in the working electrode surface of a SPE as it is depicted in Fig. 1. Initially, the working electrode was soaked in a 1% (w/v) KOH solution for 30 min, followed by air drying. The electrode was then dipped in a 10% (v/v) APTES solution in absolute ethanol for 30 min and subsequently rinsed with ethanol to remove any excess of unreacted APTES. The electrode was then placed in a laboratory stove at 110 °C for 1 h to crosslink the APTES. After cooling to room temperature, a mixture of 7.5 μL of 1.0 mg mL^{-1} EDC, 7.5 μL of 1.5 mg mL^{-1} NHS, and 5 μL of 5.0 mg mL^{-1} CQDs, all prepared in 0.01 M MES, was applied to the electrode surface and allowed to dry at room temperature. The electrode was then washed in PBS under constant shaking at 80 rpm for 20 min. Subsequently, a mixture of 10 μL of 1.0 mg mL^{-1} EDC, 10 μL of 1.5 mg mL^{-1} NHS, and 20 μL of 14 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ DD189cc Ab, all prepared in 0.01 M MES, was applied to the electrode surface, with the reaction conducted at 37 °C under constant agitation at 80 rpm. The modified SPE was washed in PBS for 30 min. Both CQDs and antibodies contain carboxylic and amine groups. The activation achieved through EDC/NHS chemistry facilitates the formation of covalent C–N bonds between the primary amine groups ($-\text{NH}_2$) of one and the activated carboxylic groups ($-\text{COOH}$) of the other. In this reaction, EDC acts as a cross-linker, while NHS serves as an activator. Finally, the electrode was incubated with a 10 mg mL^{-1} BSA solution in PBS for 1 h at 37 °C under constant agitation at 80 rpm to block non-specific binding sites that were not covered by the linked Ab to the electrode surface. The samples were then washed in PBS followed by Milli-Q water for 30 min and allowed to air dry at room temperature. The samples were stored at 4 °C until use.

Detecting D-dimer is challenging due to cross-reactivity with fibrin degradation products (FDP) and fibrinogen, leading to inconsistent results. Accurate detection requires antibodies that equally

recognize D-dimer and FDP without detecting fibrinogen. This depends on the monoclonal antibody's specificity. In this study, the DD189cc antibody was used, offering consistent specificity for various fibrin degradation products, improving D-dimer measurement precision [42].

2.4 Characterization Techniques

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was conducted on the synthesized CQD powder using a Jasco 4100 spectrophotometer, covering the range from 4000 to 600 cm^{-1} , with 64 scans per sample. The UV–VIS analysis of CQDs dissolved in Milli-Q water was performed using a Shimadzu UV-3600 spectrophotometer, spanning wavelengths from 600 to 200 nm. At a concentration of 0.125 mg L^{-1} , sharp absorbance peaks were observed.

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was also carried out on the solubilized CQD samples at the same concentration, using a J2010F TEM microscope equipped with a field emission gun. Following sonication, the sample was deposited onto a carbon-coated microgrid and allowed to dry. The diameters of the CQDs were subsequently measured using ImageJ software.

The Raman spectra were obtained using a Renishaw InVia Qontor dispersive Raman microscope spectrometer (GmbH, Germany) with Renishaw WiRE software. This spectrometer is equipped with a Leica DM2700 M optical microscope, a Peltier-cooled charge-coupled device (CCD) detector ($-70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 1024×256 pixels), and a spectrograph featuring either 2400 lines mm^{-1} or 1200 lines mm^{-1} gratings. A laser of 532 nm was used with five accumulations per sample, ten seconds of exposure time, and 5% laser power.

XPS analysis was performed the SPECS XPS system with an XR50 Al anode running at 150 W and 10 kV, MCD-9 electron detection, and the Phoibus 150 hemispherical analyzer. Casa XPS software was utilized for data analysis, with the spectra calibrated with the carbon C1s peak

binding energy set to 284.8 eV. For the elemental analysis, 3 different spots on the surface of the electrodes were measured.

The electrode surface morphology was characterized using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and atomic force microscopy (AFM). SEM analysis was performed using a Focus Ion Beam Zeiss Neon 40 instrument (Carl Zeiss, Germany) equipped with an energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectroscopy system. Samples were mounted on SEM stubs with double-sided carbon tape and coated with carbon via sputtering to enhance conductivity. Imaging was done at 5 kV with the InLens detector at various magnifications.

Topographic images of the electrode surface were captured using an AFM Dimension microscope (Bruker) with a NanoScope IV controller and a silicon TAP 150-G probe (Budget Sensors, Bulgaria). This setup operated in tapping mode at a frequency of 150 kHz and a force constant of 5 N m^{-1} . Scanning areas of $10 \times 10 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, $2 \times 2 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, and $1 \times 1 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ were imaged with a tip scanning speed of 10 mm s^{-1} and a row scanning frequency of 1 Hz. Roughness calculations were performed by analyzing sections of the images, with values of R_a (the average of the absolute surface height deviations) and R_q (the root mean square average of the height deviations from the mean plane) reported.

Water contact angle (WCA) measurements were conducted using the sessile drop method to determine the surface energy of the electrode. A $0.5 \text{ }\mu\text{L}$ droplet of Milli-Q water was placed on the electrode surface, and images were captured after stabilization at room temperature. These images were taken with the OCA 15EC instrument and analyzed using SCA20 software. The average WCA was determined from five measurements per sample.

Electrochemical characterization was performed using the Autolab PGSTAT204 controlled by the Nova software by means of cyclic voltammetry (CV). Modified SPE electrode were then

connected to the Autolab Potentiostat. CV measurements were performed at 25, 50, 100, and 200 mV s^{-1} between -0.6 to 0.8 V. The loss of electroactivity (LEA, in %) against the number of oxidation–reduction cycles was calculated using Eq 3. This parameter will help to determine the electrochemical stability of the sample:

Electrochemical characterization was conducted using an Autolab PGSTAT204 potentiostat, controlled via Nova software, through EIS and CV. All experiments were carried out at room temperature, with the modified SPE serving as the working electrode. A platinum electrode was used as the counter electrode, an Ag|AgCl electrode as the reference electrode, and a 5 mM $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6/\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ solution in PBS at pH 7.4 as the supporting electrolyte. For EIS measurements, a sinusoidal voltage with an amplitude of 10 mV was applied over a frequency range from 10^5 to 0.1 Hz. CV experiments were conducted at scan rates of 25, 50, 100, and 200 mV s^{-1} within a potential window of -0.6 to 0.8 V. The loss of electroactivity (LEA, in %) with respect to the number of oxidation–reduction cycles was calculated using Eq. 1. This parameter is crucial for assessing the electrochemical stability of the electrode.

$$LEA = \frac{\Delta Q}{Q_5} = \frac{Q_5 - Q_{100}}{Q_5} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where ΔQ is the difference between the oxidation charge (in C) of the fifth (Q_5) and final evaluated oxidation–reduction cycle (Q_{100}). Usually the initial cycles at the experimental level are discarded, since a structural relaxation of the polymer that contains the hydrogel is always necessary, which takes place in these steps.

2.5 Impedance-based Immunosensor Testing

The immunosensing test was conducted by preparing various concentrations of 80D70 DD antigen in PBS (10, 25, 50, 75, 100, 250, 750, 500, and 1000 ng mL^{-1}). The DD antigen solutions

were incubated with the sensor at 37 °C for 1 h. Following each incubation period, the sensor was washed with PBS. EIS measurements were then performed in a solution containing 5 mM $K_3Fe(CN)_6/K_4Fe(CN)_6$ solution in PBS at pH 7.4, using a sinusoidal voltage of 10 mV across a frequency range from 10^5 to 0.1 Hz.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 CQD characterization

The CQDs were synthesized via a hydrothermal method and characterized using FTIR, UV–VIS, and TEM analyses. First, FTIR analysis was conducted on the purified CQDs to identify surface functional groups (Fig. 2a). Strong peaks at 3433 and 3348 cm^{-1} correspond to hydrophilic N–H and O–H groups, respectively, confirming the excellent solubility of CQDs in aqueous environments [43]. The peak at 3205 cm^{-1} can be attributed to aliphatic C–H [44]. Additional peaks at 1580, 1450, 1410, and 1160 cm^{-1} are associated with C=O, C–N stretching, and C–O vibrational stretching, respectively [43, 45, 46].

For the UV–VIS analysis, the CQDs were dissolved in Milli-Q water at a concentration of 0.125 $ng\ mL^{-1}$ (Fig. 2b). The UV–VIS spectrum revealed two shoulder peaks at 255 and 280 nm, corresponding to the $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions of C=C bonds [41, 47, 48]. Additionally, absorbance bands at 340 and 410 nm indicated $n-\pi^*$ transitions of N=O and C=O bonds, with a maximum absorbance at 210 nm attributed to the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of sp^2 aromatic domains. Finally, TEM analysis of the aqueous CQD solution (Fig. 2c and 2d) revealed spherical CQDs with an average diameter of 2.1 \pm 0.4 nm.

Fig. 2. Characterization of CQDs: a) FTIR, b) UV-VIS absorbance, c) particle size distribution, d) TEM micrograph

3.2 Sensor Fabrication

Fig. 1 illustrates the fabrication process of the biosensor. The electrode design is based on a SPE functionalized with CQDs and DD Ab in successive layers to achieve high sensitivity and specificity for the DD antigen. The working electrode features an initial layer of carbon, which is activated with KOH. This activated surface is then reacted with APTES to introduce amino groups, which can condense with the carboxylic groups on the CQDs' surface [41, 49]. The CQDs are covalently linked to the surface via amide bond formation using an EDC/NHS mixture, creating a

CQD monolayer. The conductive nature of the CQD layer reduces the electrode's resistance, enhancing sensitivity to small impedance changes caused by low antigen concentrations. Next, DD

Ab are immobilized onto the CQD monolayer (Fig. 3). The abundant carboxylic and amine groups on the CQD surface facilitate this immobilization [41, 49]. Finally, BSA protein is applied as a blocking agent to prevent nonspecific binding of antigens to the non-functionalized areas of the CQD layer.

Fig. 3. A schematic diagram of the fabricated CQD-based impedance multilayer immunosensor is shown, featuring a CQD layer, an Ab layer, a BSA blocking layer, and the DD antigen upon detection.

3.3 Sensor Characterization

Raman spectroscopy was employed to examine the surface of the carbon SPE after each functionalization step, as shown in Fig. 4. The initial Raman spectrum of the carbon SPE exhibits the two characteristic graphite peaks at 1360 cm^{-1} and 1580 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the D and G bands, respectively [50]. The G band, the primary mode of graphite, is associated with the symmetric E_{2g} Raman mode, corresponding to the absorption band of planar sp^2 carbon network.

The D band, a defect-induced Raman feature, is related to the A_{1g} breathing mode and can be observed in disordered graphitic materials. This band is linked to the breathing mode of sp^2 carbon rings [50-52]. Following the formation of the APTES monolayer, the carbonaceous bands disappear, and new bands appear at 860 cm^{-1} , 950 cm^{-1} , 1120 cm^{-1} , and 1510 cm^{-1} . These correspond to the asymmetric stretching of SiO_4 , stretching of Si-OH , stretching of C-N , and bending of NH_2 , respectively (Fig. S1) [53].

Fig. 4. Raman spectra of the SPE after each functionalization step.

The subsequent formation of the CQD layer, facilitated by bonding to the surface through the APTES-functionalized SPE electrode (hereafter SPE/CQD), is confirmed by the reappearance of the characteristic D and G bands observed in the pristine SPE electrode, attributable to the graphitic nature of the CQDs [54]. In this case, the G and D bands appear sharper and more pronounced due

to the increased graphitic composition resulting from the deposition and aggregation of CQDs on the surface [55]. The shift in the APTES bands and the reemergence of the D and G bands upon the addition of the CQD layer indicate the interaction between the CQD and APTES layers. The Raman spectrum of the CQD layer closely resembles those reported in previous studies [54].

The successful deposition of Ab on the electrode surface is indicated by the appearance of two characteristic peaks: 1650 cm^{-1} and 1298 cm^{-1} , corresponding to amide I and amide III bands, respectively [56]. Likewise, the presence of BSA on the electrode surface is confirmed by the same characteristic bands.

Fig. 5. a) XPS analysis of O, N and C elements and b) Water contact angle of the SPE after each surface functionalization step

The functionalization stages were further verified using XPS analysis. Peak deconvolution of the XPS spectra for C, O and N elements was performed (Fig. 5a). In the SPE layer, the C1s spectrum was deconvoluted into three components at 284.9 eV, 286.3 eV, and a minor peak at 289.3 eV (Fig. S2). These peaks are attributed to C–H, C–C, and C=C bonds for the first band [57, 58], C–O for the second peak, and C=O–O for the third [59]. Similarly, the C1s spectrum of the CQD layer shows three peaks at 284.6 eV, 285.9 eV, and 288.2 eV. The first two peaks correspond

to those of the SPE layer, while the 288.2 eV peak can be attributed to N–C=O and partially to C=O–O. Upon adding the CQD layer, the C1s spectrum further deconvolutes into four peaks at 284.7 eV, 286.2 eV, 288.2 eV, and 289.4 eV. The first two peaks remain consistent with those of the SPE, while the 288.2 eV peak is clearly associated with N–C=O, and the 289.4 eV peak corresponds to C=O–O, indicating the presence of amide bonds and carboxylic groups from the Ab structures. Finally, the BSA layer shows three deconvoluted peaks at 284.8 eV, 286.2 eV, and 288.0 eV, closely resembling those observed in the Ab deposition layer.

Deconvolution of the O1s spectra for all surfaces revealed two consistent peaks around 530–531 eV and 531–532 eV, corresponding to C=O and C–O bonds, respectively (Fig. S3) [60]. Except for the CQD layer, the C=O peak shows a higher concentration compared to C–O, indicating an abundance of carboxylic groups. This is expected for the Ab and BSA layers, given the presence of carboxylic terminals and amide bonds in protein structures. Additionally, deconvolution of the N1s spectra for the CQD, Ab, and BSA layers displayed similar features (Fig. S4). All spectra exhibited a prominent peak at around 399 eV, attributed to amine groups, and a smaller peak near 400 eV, corresponding to amide groups [61].

The nature of the chemical groups present on the electrode surface significantly influences its hydrophobic or hydrophilic behavior. The water contact angle (WCA) is a crucial parameter that allows us to measure changes in surface hydrophilicity resulting from surface functionalization. Fig. 5b illustrates the WCA results for both the pristine SPE and after the CQD monolayer deposition. It is clearly observed that the untreated SPE is highly hydrophobic, with a contact angle of $122.0^\circ \pm 1.9^\circ$. In contrast, the deposition of the CQD film on the SPE drastically increases its hydrophilicity, reducing the contact angle to $54.5^\circ \pm 3.4^\circ$. This significant change is attributed to the highly hydrophilic nature of CQDs, which is imparted by the –COOH and –NH groups on their

surface [41]. Following the formation of the sensitive Ab layer, and the subsequent application of BSA to cover the non-functionalized areas of the surface, the WCA changes to $56.0^\circ \pm 4.0$ and $75.1^\circ \pm 4.3$, respectively. The slight decrease in hydrophilicity observed after the addition of the Ab and BSA layers may be attributed to a shielding effect, where the hydrophilic groups on the CQD surface are masked by the aggregated proteins. This aggregation exposes higher density of hydrophobic regions on the Ab and BSA surface, leading to an overall increase in surface hydrophobicity.

Morphological information was obtained through SEM micrographs and AFM topographies of the electrode surface after each immobilization step. Fig. S5 presents SEM images at two different magnifications, comparing the pristine SPE electrode and SPE/CQD modified electrode. The SEM micrographs reveal that the surface of the pristine SPE working electrode is composed of very fine granular structures, attributable to the ultrafine carbon particles constituting the electrode. Following the addition of the CQD layer, a film-like layer is observable on top of the granular carbon layer. This film is the combination of the CQDs covalently linked to the surface via APTES. Additionally, larger granular structures, not present on the bare SPE, appear in the micrographs after the introduction of the CQD layer. These larger granules indicate the presence of CQD aggregates.

The surface topography of the nanoscale electrode after each immobilization step is illustrated in Fig. 6 using AFM microscopy. The changes in the surface were monitored through roughness measurements based on the micrograph images obtained. Specifically, the root mean square average of height deviation from the mean image data plane (R_q) and the arithmetic average of the absolute values of surface height deviations from the mean plane (R_a) were recorded (Table 1).

Fig. 6. AFM topography images ($1 \times 1 \mu\text{m}^2$) of the fabricated immunosensor electrode taken after each functionalization step. The images presented are from the height channel, shown in both 2D (top) and 3D (bottom) representations. These images include: the pristine SPE electrode, after CQD monolayer formation, following Ab immobilization, and after the subsequent addition of the BSA layer to cover potential voids in the Ab monolayer.

Table 1. R_q and R_a roughness values calculated from the AFM micrographs of $1 \times 1 \mu\text{m}^2$

	SPE	SPE/CQD	SPE/CQD/Ab	SPE/CQD/Ab/BSA
				A
R_q (nm)	98 ± 30	115 ± 48	198 ± 103	70 ± 11
R_a (nm)	78 ± 21	93 ± 38	152 ± 79	55 ± 9

An increase in the roughness of the electrode was observed upon the addition of the CQD layer, likely due to the added rugosity of both CQD nanoparticles and their aggregates on the electrode surface. The subsequent addition of the Ab layer further increased the electrode's roughness. Given the low concentration used for Ab immobilization, the orientation of the Ab on the electrode

surface is likely non-uniform, with some Ab upright and others lying horizontally, leading to increased roughness [62].

Conversely, the addition of the BSA layer resulted in a decrease in roughness with low standard deviations. This more even and lower roughness surface can be attributed to the high concentration of the blocking solution used, which promotes a more densely packed and homogeneous coverage on the electrode surface [62].

Finally, EIS technique was used to characterize the electrode after each functionalization step. The Nyquist plot (Fig. 7a) of the bare SPE exhibits a semicircle at high frequencies and a linear section at low frequencies. The semicircle represents the electron transfer resistance and the behavior of the double-layer capacitor, while the linear part at low frequencies is indicative of a diffusion-limited process [63].

Upon the addition of the CQD layer, the diameter of the semicircle is greatly reduced, signifying improved conductivity of the electrode and a decrease in double layer formation [64]. This enhancement in conductivity is attributed to the conductive properties of the CQD layer. At higher frequencies (Fig. 7a inset), a new, very small semicircle emerges with the CQD layer addition, suggesting a new charge transfer interface between the electrolyte and the CQD layer. The charge transfer resistance at this new interface is very low, reflecting the thin and highly conductive nature of the CQD layer. This layer is so thin that it is almost imperceptible in the Bode phase diagram, only becoming noticeable when the Bode phase diagram of the CQD layer is plotted separately (Fig. 7c inset).

Fig. 7. EIS plots of the immunosensor after each functionalization step: (a) Nyquist plot with an inset showing the highest frequency range, (b) Bode impedance plot, and (c) Bode phase plot with an inset of the CQD sample and its fitting. (d) Electronic equivalent circuits: (d1) for the SPE electrode, and (d2) for the SPE electrode with the additional layers of CQD, Ab, and BSA. The scatter plots represent the experimental data, while the lines represent the simulated data from the fitting.

Functionalizing the CQD layer with Ab increased the diameters of the two observed semicircles. This increase is to be expected, as the Ab layer acts as an insulating layer, reducing electron transfer across the electrolyte-electrode interface (small semicircle) and through the bulk of the

electrode (large semicircle). Likewise, adding the BSA surface blocking layer resulted in a further increase in the semicircle diameters. These surface modifications are also evident in the Bode impedance (Fig. 7b) and Bode phase (Fig. 7c) diagrams. More specifically, the Bode impedance plot shows a notable decrease in impedance at low frequencies after the CQD layer is added, followed by an increase in impedance with the addition of the Ab and BSA layers. On the other hand, the Bode phase diagram displays a shift in the main peak, originally around 700 Hz for the bare SPE. The redox reaction of $K_3Fe(CN)_6/K_4Fe(CN)_6$ has a specific time constant depending on the electrode, with faster reactions occurring at higher frequencies. The addition of layers on the SPE surface delays this redox reaction to lower frequencies being more dependent on the diffusion process. This is observed in the system, where the peak shifts to around 3 Hz for the CQD layer, 1 Hz for the Ab layer, and 0.9 Hz for the BSA layer. Additionally, the second semicircle in the Nyquist plot is reflected by a small peak around 100 Hz in the Bode phase diagram after the Ab layer is added, with its intensity increasing and shifting to 100 Hz upon the addition of the BSA layer.

The EIS spectra for all functionalization steps during the immunosensor electrode fabrication were modeled using two different Randles circuits. The electronic equivalent circuit (EEC) schemes are illustrated in Fig. 7d and the values of the fitted elements are detailed in Table 2. The bare SPE EEC was modeled as a cell where polarization results from a combination of kinetic and diffusion processes. This circuit consists of a resistor (R_s) in series with a parallel connection of a constant phase element (CPE_B) and a resistor (R_B) in series with another constant phase element (CPE_w) (see Fig. 7-d1)) [63]. The second semicircle observed on the Nyquist plot upon the addition of the CQD, Ab, and BSA layers was modeled by adding another parallel connection, composed of a resistor (R_{INT}) and a CPE (CPE_{INT}) as depicted in Fig. 7-d2. The resistance R_s represents the

electrolyte resistance of the $K_3Fe(CN)_6/K_4Fe(CN)_6$ solution used during the measurements, while the resistance R_B represents the charge transfer resistance into the porous carbon electrode.

The constant phase element CPE_B models an imperfect double-layer capacitor. This non-ideal behavior stems from the rugosity and porosity of the carbon electrode. An n -value of 1 for the CPE indicates an ideal capacitor, while an n -value closer to 0 indicates an ideal resistor. In this case, all CPE_B values are very close to 1, indicating behavior similar to that of an ideal capacitor. The third constant phase element (CPE_W) represents a non-ideal Warburg-like diffusion, characterized by an n -value approaching 0.5. This behavior is consistently observed after each surface modification of the electrode [65, 66].

Table 2. Values of resistances and capacitances, for each sample analyzed by EIS, and obtained after fitting the EEC displayed in Fig. 7d. The fitting error (in %) is indicated in parentheses.

	R_s	R_{INT}	CPE_{INT}		R_B	CPE_B		CPE_W		χ^2
	R (Ω)	R (Ω)	Y0 ($\mu F s^{n-1}$)	n	R (Ω)	Y0 ($\mu F s^{n-1}$)	n	Y0 ($\mu F s^{n-1}$)	n	
SPE	183.6 (0.3)	-	-	-	823.8 (0.5)	1200 (2.3)	0.97 (0.3)	1765.7 (0.9)	0.43 (1.5)	0.0029
SPE/CQD	209.0 (0.4)	29.2 (6.6)	172.0 (31.0)	0.63 (6.4)	323.6 (3.7)	255.9 (3.0)	0.93 (0.6)	2658.0 (1.7)	0.49 (1.9)	0.0006
SPE/CQD/Ab	200.9 (0.4)	40.4 (7.1)	588.7 (24.8)	0.59 (5.8)	452.3 (5.9)	324.5 (3.5)	0.96 (0.9)	2722.5 (4.4)	0.50 (4.1)	0.0009
SPE/CQD/Ab/BSA	207.1 (0.4)	67.1 (4.1)	96.3 (13.3)	0.77 (2.7)	595.2 (6.3)	289.0 (1.7)	0.95 (0.9)	2732.8 (6.6)	0.50 (6.0)	0.0012

R_{INT} represents the charge transfer resistance from the electrolyte solution to the newly formed interfacial layer, while CPE_{INT} represents the capacitive behavior of this layer. As shown in Table

2, the R_{INT} values increase with the addition of the Ab and BSA layers on the CQD layer. This is expected because both the Ab and BSA layers form impedimetric layers, hence increasing the charge transfer resistance. Additionally, the n -value of CPE_{INT} is lowest for the Ab layer, followed by the CQD and then the BSA layer. A lower n -value indicates less ideal capacitive behavior, which correlates with the electrode's surface morphology. These n -values align with the roughness values obtained from AFM data, where the Ab layer had the highest roughness, followed by the CQD layer, and finally the BSA layer.

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) was conducted after each step of the fabrication process at varying scan rates (Fig. S6). The CV of the SPE/CQD layer exhibited two distinct peaks corresponding to the redox couple of $K_3Fe(CN)_6/K_4Fe(CN)_6$, with a peak separation of 0.22 V at a scan rate of 50 $mV s^{-1}$. However, upon the deposition of the Ab and BSA layers, the intensity of these peaks decreased, accompanied by an increase in the peak-to-peak separation. This behavior can be attributed to the shielding effect caused by the non-conductive nature of the protein layers [67, 68]. Interestingly, the reduction in redox peak intensity and the increase in peak separation were more pronounced with the BSA layer compared to the Ab layer, likely due to the higher concentration of BSA used in the fabrication. Additionally, an extra pair of redox peaks appeared following the deposition of the Ab layer at scan rates starting from 50 $mV s^{-1}$, and from 25 $mV s^{-1}$ for the BSA layer. This new pair of peaks may result from the increased presence of amine groups on the electrode surface, which enhance interactions with $[Fe(CN)_6]^{3-}$ [69]. However, the overall electroactivity of the electrode remained limited due to the insulating nature of the protein layers.

Finally, the stability of the fabricated sensor was evaluated by performing CV at a scan rate of 100 $mV s^{-1}$ for 100 cycles (Fig. S7). The loss of electroactivity (LEA) was calculated as the relative

change in the area under the CV curve at the 100th cycle compared to the 5th cycle (Eq. 1). The calculated LEA was just 2.6%, demonstrating the exceptional stability of the device.

3.4 Electrochemical Sensor

The immunosensor was developed to detect DD antigens in serum samples. Varying antigen concentrations were quantified by monitoring changes in the response value of the EIS spectrum. This process aimed to establish the range and limit of detection (LoD) of the immunosensor.

Fig. 8. a) Nyquist plots of SPE/CQD/Ab/BSA immunosensor incubated at increasing DD antigen concentrations. b) Calibration curve for DD antigen concentrations ranging from 10 to 1000 ng mL⁻¹ in a PBS solution using the SPE/CQD/Ab/BSA immunosensor electrode.

Impedance measurements, depicted via the Nyquist plot in Fig. 8a, revealed that the binding of the DD antigen to the Ab on the electrode surface created additional resistance for charge transfer, increasing the second semi-circle diameter corresponding to the bulk charge transfer (R_B parameter in the Randles circuit). This increase in resistance was used to obtain the calibration curve for DD antigen concentration by plotting the relative change in the R_{INT} parameter, derived from the EEC of EIS spectra, as a function of antigen concentration (Fig. 8b).

Table 3. Comparison of the analytical parameters obtained using EIS spectroscopy and modified immunosensors for the determination of DD antigen.

Immunosensor	Detection range (ng mL⁻¹)	LOD (ng mL⁻¹)	Ref.
SPE/Au Nps	1 – 500	8.9	[32]
Fe NPs	1 – 50	0.5	[70]
Au/SWCNT-COOH	10 ⁻⁴ – 2000	10 ⁻⁴	[29]
PPy/ANTA/Cu ²⁺	0.1 – 500	0.1	[30]
Au/Ferrocene	1 – 1000	0.01	[71]
Au NPs	0 – 1000	2.0	[31]
SPE/CQD	10 – 1000	13.4	This work

SPE: screen printed electrode, NPs: nanoparticles, SWCNT: single walled carbon nanotube, PPy: poly pyrrol, ANTA: N-alpha-bis(carboxymethyl)-l-lysine hydrate, CQD: carbon quantum dot.

The calibration curve shows that the SPE/CQD/Ab/BSA sensor works in two linear regions, with correlation coefficient $R^2 = 0.9832$ and 0.9862 for concentrations ranging from $10 - 100 \text{ ng mL}^{-1}$ and $100 - 1000 \text{ ng mL}^{-1}$. The limit of detection (at $s/N=3$) obtained in the first regime for the plot displayed in Fig. 8b was as low as 13.4 ng mL^{-1} . The performance of SPE/CQD/Ab/BSA immunosensor was compared with previous immunosensors based on Ab and EIS DD antigen detection reported in the literature (Table 3). The incorporation of CQDs as a carbonaceous material between the SPE base electrode and the Ab enhances the electrochemical signal, resulting in detection ranges comparable to those of previous DD sensors that utilize the same EIS technique, though with a slightly higher detection limit, except in the case of the Au/SWCNT-COOH immunosensor which presents a high sensitivity with a very small LOD and a wider detection range due to the optimal electrochemical shielding induced by the antigen [29]. However, the key

advantage of the present CQD-based immunosensor is its lower fabrication cost and simplicity compared to other immunosensors that rely on the same technique.

As illustrated in Fig. 8a, the increase in resistance is not sizeable. This could be attributed to the low concentration of Ab immobilized on the electrode surface and the low antigen concentration ranges used in the study. Utilizing low Ab concentrations is advantageous as it reduces the manufacturing cost of the sensor. However, low concentrations can also lead to decreased sensitivity and saturation at lower antigen levels. Hence, a compromise between cost and sensitivity is necessary. Nevertheless, despite the low surface Ab concentrations, the CQD-based device demonstrated a good response at low antigen concentrations, as shown in Fig. 8b.

Finally, the sensor successfully was used to quantify the DD concentration in the plasma of a healthy patient (126 ng mL^{-1}). For these initial tests, the plasma was diluted with PBS at a 1:3 ratio and incubated with the sensor. The calculated recovery rates ranged between 60-70%, demonstrating the sensor's ability to detect DD in a complex biological matrix. While the recovery rates were influenced by the matrix effect—a known challenge in biological sample analysis caused by the presence of other molecules [72]—this is a common obstacle in bioanalytical assays. Factors such as the choice of diluent, dilution factor, patient-to-patient variability, and sample recovery method can influence the matrix effect [73]. Encouragingly, these results indicate that the sensor achieves a satisfactory level of recovery for DD from human plasma, even in the presence of biological noise. Further optimization of key parameters, such as dilution protocols and sample preparation, holds great potential to enhance recovery rates. These promising findings highlight the sensor's potential for reliable quantification of DD in clinical samples.

Future research on CQDs in immunosensors could enhance their versatility by exploring diverse functional groups. Their ease of functionalization with antibodies makes them ideal for targeted

applications. Integrating CQDs with various biomarkers could expand their use across diagnostic fields, enabling the development of highly sensitive and selective sensors for early disease detection. Optimizing CQD platforms for multi-analyte detection and improving stability through novel conjugation strategies could advance biosensing technologies.

4. Conclusions

A carbon SPE was functionalized with CQDs and DD Ab to create a highly sensitive and specific biosensor for DD antigens. The fabrication process included activating the carbon surface with KOH, introducing amino groups using APTES, covalently linking CQDs via an EDC/NHS mixture, and immobilizing DD Ab onto the CQD monolayer. BSA protein was applied as a blocking agent to prevent nonspecific binding.

Raman spectroscopy confirmed each functionalization step, with changes in characteristic peaks indicating successful layer formation. WCA measurements showed that the pristine SPE was highly hydrophobic, which changed to more hydrophilic upon CQD layer deposition. SEM and AFM analyses revealed changes in surface morphology and increased roughness with each added layer, particularly after CQD and Ab immobilization. EIS indicated improved conductivity with CQD addition and increased resistance with Ab and BSA layers, confirming effective functionalization.

The biosensor demonstrated effective detection of DD antigens through changes in impedance, as shown in Nyquist and Bode plots. A calibration curve was established for DD antigen concentrations ranging from 10 to 1000 ng mL⁻¹, with a two defined linear regions with a LoD of 13.4 ng mL⁻¹. The use of CQDs improved electrode sensitivity due to their conductive properties. Low Ab concentrations reduced manufacturing costs but also resulted in modest increases in

resistance, indicating a trade-off between cost and sensitivity. The biosensor's performance was compared with other electrochemical DD antigen detection methods, demonstrating competitive sensitivity and specificity. Overall, the study presents a detailed methodology for fabricating and characterizing a sensitive CQD-based impedance immunosensor for DD antigen detection, highlighting its advantages in terms of sensitivity, cost-effectiveness, and potential clinical application.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information.

The online version contains additional Figures of Raman spectroscopy, XPS deconvolution, and SEM micrographs.

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